

EFFECT OF SWEETENER IN THE FORMULATION OF CHOCOLATE WHEY PROTEIN CONCENTRATE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to discuss on the sweetness aspect of chocolate whey protein powder formulation. The trails for the analysis is carried out with two different sweeteners which are , sucralose and Nuva sweet 600. The sweetener aspect in the Chocolate flavored whey protein powder has been evaluated by trails for its dispersibility and the sensory characteristic for the analysis are studied. Among the two sweeteners, it was found that Nuva 600 sweet has more preferable sweetness and overall acceptability than sucralose of the two samples.

Keywords: *whey protein concentrate(WPC),whey protein isolate(WPI), sweetener, xanthan gum, Carboxymethyl Cellulose.*

INTRODUCTION

Whey proteins are renowned for their great nutritional content and numerous food-product applications. Whey proteins' structural and biological roles are connected to their nutritional and functional properties. (J. N. de WIT 1998) . The whey proteins are obtained from whey, which is a yellow/green liquid protein remaining after coagulation and separation of caseins from the milk by enzyme (chymosin) or acid (mineral/organic) during the cheese-making process (Smithers, 2008). The liquid that is left over after milk has been strained and allowed to curdle is called whey. It results from the casein or cheese-making process as a byproduct. Following processing, whey comes in three main forms that are sold on the market: WPC contains less fat and carbohydrate. WPC has varying amounts of protein depending on its level of concentration. The average amount of protein in concentrates varies between 30% and 90%, depending on their price. To eliminate all the fat and lactose, WPI require extra processing. At least 90% of the protein in WPI is normal. The term "predigested" refers to whey protein hydrolysate (WPH), which has already undergone partial hydrolysis, a process necessary for the body to absorb protein. Compared to the other two whey protein forms, WPH digests more fast. One of the two

types of artificial sweeteners used in the analysis was sucralose, a non-caloric sweetener and sugar alternative. In the European Union, it is also referred as E955. When sucrose is chlorinated, three of the hydroxy groups in the C1, C4, and C6 positions are replaced, resulting in a 1,6-dichloro-1,6-dideoxyfructose-4-chloro-deoxygalactose disaccharide. Sucralose is 320–1,000 times sweeter than sucrose. Nuva sweet 600, a reasonably priced sugar alternative, satisfies consumer's demands for exquisite sweetness without adding calories. Its high sweetness intensity allows for a significant reduction in the amount of actual sugar while still reproducing the proper sugar profiles for a range of applications.

Table 1. formulation ingredients percentage of chocolate whey protein concentrate.

S.NO.	INGREDIENTS	Percentage(%)
1.	Whey protein concentrate	83.90
2.	whey protein isolate	5.00
3.	Xanthum gum	0.35
4.	CMC	0.44
5.	Digestive enzyme	0.07
6.	Sweetener	0.05
7.	Milk powder	4.43
8.	Salt	0.62
9.	Silica	0.30
10.	Cocoa powder	2.92
11.	Chocolate flavor powder	0.79

To make the chocolate whey protein concentrate more palatable, sweetener is used. The Nuva sweetener from nuvanto bioscience private limited in Bengaluru, Karnataka. Manually measuring the whey protein dispersibility, for which the vertical and horizontal counts were taken. A protein's solubility characteristics impact how it will be used in meals in the future. (Heidi Lightfoot 2018). The ability to scatter in water is referred to as dispersibility. The objective of the study is to evaluate the effect of sweetener in the formulation of chocolate whey protein concentrate.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The analysis was carried out with whey protein concentrate, whey protein isolate, Xanthan gum, CMC Powder (Carboxymethyl Cellulose), digestive enzymes, milk powder, fine salt powder, silica, Cocoa powder, Chocolate flavor powder, and Sweetener:

- a. Sucralose,
- b. Nuva sweet 600

Samples are made by mixing all the dry ingredients together , except the sweeteners. For the sample A which comprise of sucralose sweetener while sample B comprise of Nuva sweet 600.

PROCESS METHODOLOGY:

Weighing the dry ingredients

Fig 1.Methodology involved in the formulation.

Method For the shake preparation:

Add 33 g of finished product to a 150 ml glass of milk/ lukewarm water . Shake it well , with a shaker without any lumps formation.

Sensory analysis

A panel of Five untrained people participated in the consumer study. sensory evaluation was conducted at samath global food consultant pvt ltd, Hyderabad . The protein concentrate sample A and sample B are offered to the panelist and marked for the point of 5 hedonic scale to determine the degree of parameters like sweetness, consistency, taste, flavor, color and overall acceptability analysis used to determine the statistical

significance of sweeteners in chocolate whey protein concentrate.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The sensory scores for two samples were graphically represented (refer fig.1) on 5 point hedonic scale. The score for sweetness, consistency, taste, flavor, color and overall acceptability are given. The total average sensory for the samples which seems to be highest for sample B , which has Nuva 600 sweet and while minimum score was observed for sample A, which has sucralose.

We observed that the dispersibility for the sample B with Nuva 600 sweet is better than sample A sucralose

Fig. 2 sensory evaluation of sample A & sample

From the below Table 2, we observed a better dispersibility of sample B than sample A when dissolved in water and milk.

Table 2. dispersibility test values for both sample

TRAILS	DISPERSIBILTY	
	Water	Milk
Sample A	Horizontal-5 vertical-5	Horizontal-7 vertical-7
Sample B	Horizontal-4 vertical-4	Horizontal-6 vertical-6

The ingredients used for stabilizer, thickener, sweetener are optimized with varying percentage. The xanthan gum used for the whey protein formulation are inferred as, The equivalent ideal cheese whey produced 12.8 g/L of xanthan as a result.. (Seyyed Vahid Niknezhad et al 2015). Based on creep, it was shown that the ideal amount of xanthan gum for instant pudding is 13.5%. (Mahmut Dogan et al 2014). 0.27% w/w xanthan gum content orange beverage (Hamed Mirhosseini et al 2008). The carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) utilised for the whey protein formulation is inferred since responses were achieved at 3% CMC concentration. Surface methodology (RSM) was used to estimate the effects and to optimise the Mushroom Slices with concentrations of CMC (0-3% w/w). (Somayeh Taghian Dinani et al 2014). The whey protein formulation's sucralose is implied to be, The optimal sucralose concentrations for the greatest sensory qualities were 3.5% and 3.0%, respectively. (Dhanya Suresh et al 2022). In the range of spiked levels, 94.28%-107.16%. The limit of detection of sucralose was 0.0024 g/kg for beverage.. (Li Sang et al 2018).

CONCLUSION

Based on the data collected, it can be inferred that sample B which contains Nuva sweet 600 has shown the greater acceptability than the sample A with sucralose. Sample B with Nuva sweet 600 has a greater quality of sweetness, flavour, consistency, colour, and overall acceptability over sample A. Hence it is concluded that Nuva sweet 600 is chosen for enhanced quality in chocolate whey protein concentrate formulation.

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